

Raglai

By Isvan Quang, Van Lang university

Entry tags: Vietnam, Religious Group, Southeast Asian Religions

The Raglai are an ethnic minority religious community in Vietnam. In the 20th century, many Raglai converted to Christianity. This entry focuses on traditional Raglai Religion. They live in Lam Dong, Ninh Thuận, Binh Thuan, Ninh Thuan (57.442 people), and Khanh Hoa Provinces of the South Central Vietnam. Similar to the Cham, Churu, Rade and Jarai languages, Raglai is classified as a Chamic language in the Malayo-Polynesian branch of the Austronesian language family. The traditional life of the Raglai people is mostly concentrated in a small village (puk) or a village (palei) on high, flat land and near sources of fresh water. Each village usually consists of several dozen roofs/small houses. The members of Raglai family usually include a father, mother and unmarried children. A head of the village is called a "Po Palei," usually the one who first developed the land or their descendent. Village chiefs are responsible for making offerings to heaven and earth during severe drought. The most prestigious person in the family are called "Ong Kei Palei" (village elders). The village elders run all activities, preside over festivals, and organize a teams to prevent wild beasts as well as invading forces.

Date Range: 1160 CE - 2017 CE

Region: South Central Vietnam

Region tags: Vietnam, Binh Thuan, Lam Dong, Binh Thuan, Ninh Thuan

This region is mostly the mountainous area and forest. Therefore, the Cham calls them "Raglai" which means the "forest" people. Ninh Thuan Province where the most Raglai community live is the boundary of other 3 provinces. Raglai live the East of Lam Dong province (near the Raglai community in the West of Ninh Thuan Province), the North of Binh Thuan province (Near the Raglai in the South of Ninh Thuan), and the South of Khanh Hoa Province (near the Raglai community in the North of Ninh Thuan).

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Nguyen Tuan Triet (1991), The Raglai people in Vietnam, 151p. KHXH, HCM City.
- Source 2: Phan Xuan Bien, Phan An, Phan Van Dop, Vo Cong Nguyen, Nguyen Van Hue (1998), Culture and Society of the Raglai Community in Vietnam. 346p, KHXH, HCM City.
- Source 3: Phan Quoc Anh (2007), The Raglai Culture - what remains. 341p, VHDT, Ha Noi.

Notes: Nguyễn Hữu Bài, et. al. 2014. Văn hóa dân gian Raglai ở Khanh Hòa. Hồ Chí Minh City: Nhà xuất bản văn hóa - văn nghệ. ISBN 978-604-68-1078-0

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://dulichkhanhson.vn/bao-ton/>

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 3 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MDjW9QH31_s&feature=emb_title

– Source 3 Description: Bamboo Basket carrying Bag

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Seen as a part of the Chamic family, the Raglai also share some similarities with Cham communities such as open conflicts with Vietnamese culture. This has resulted from a history of Vietnamese conquest of Cham and Raglai lands.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Seen as a part of the Cham, the Raglai also share some similarities as the Cham such as Open conflict with Vietnamese culture. Vietnamese conquest of Cham/Raglai lands

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Most are animist and polytheist. They also believe in various nature spirits. The state does not recognise this belief as an official religion of the Raglai, so that there is no support for this belief but the state supports for development projects to enhance the lives of this community. The Raglai may have historically and contemporarily benefitted from meager state support given to Cham communities.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 122.245

Notes: This number of the Raglai is based on the report of the General Statistics Office of Vietnam of the State in 2009. Every ten years, the Vietnamese state conducts a census. The results of the 2019 census are not yet available.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: According to the General Statistics in 2009, there 122.245 Raglai people in Vietnam. 50% the population lived in Ninh Thuan and Khanh Hoa Provinces. In Ninh Thuan, the Raglai population was 58,911 people accounting for 48,2% of the Raglai in Vietnam while Khanh Hoa had 45,915 people, accounting for 37,6%, Binh Thuan Province had 15,440 people and Lam Dong had 1,517 people.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– No

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Yes

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– No

- ↳ A political leader chooses the leader:
 - No
- ↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:
 - Yes
- ↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:
 - No

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:
– No

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:
– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Raglai have only 'oral scriptures' traditionally, although many of these oral texts were written down in Romanized Raglai language in the 20th and 21st centuries.

↳ Are they written:
– Yes

↳ Are they oral:
– Yes

Notes: Oral texts plus non-standard romanized versions of traditions have begun to be accumulated from the 1960s-present. However, because Romanization was introduced by Christian missionaries, this is the period when we begin to see traditional religions blended

with Christianity more, and Protestant Christianity begins to become more popular.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Field doesn't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 4

Notes: 4m-5m for a settlement, not include the outdoor space of the structure.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 2.5

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 40

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:
– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:
– No

↳ Temples:
– No

↳ Altars:
– No

↳ Devotional markers:
– No

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:
– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:
– Yes [specify]: There are also ancestral graveyards/houses (Kago) associated with each village and town, of great importance. This is the most prominent image in Raglai culture

Is iconography present:

– No

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– No

Notes: The dead will go to the ancestor realm and live like the living people. There are distinct realms for the dead and the living.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: All powerful. Determines nature of all saints.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes

 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - No

 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes

- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
- ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
- ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can be seen:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:
 - Yes
- ↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - No
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through specialists:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
 - ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
 - No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what

you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

- Yes

- ↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:
 - No
- ↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Yes

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society
– All individuals within contemporary world
– All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:
– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):
– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes

- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
 - Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
 - Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Cooperation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
 - Yes

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Yes

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Yes

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– No

↳ Monogamy (females):

– No

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is tempered by historical polygamy. Additionally, divorce allows monogamy to be tempered in early modern and modern periods. Sex with members of the same clan (village or hometown) is taboo.

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: Monogamy is tempered by historical polygamy. Additionally, divorce allows monogamy to be tempered in early modern and modern periods. Sex with members of the same clan (village or hometown) is taboo.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– Yes

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– Yes [specify]: food

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Members of the community should go to attend and support for rituals (including marriages) of families and other families. This connection is widely popular in this community.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 40

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 6

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

↳ Hair:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dress:
– Yes

↳ Ornaments:
– Yes

↳ Archaic ritual language:
– Yes

↳ Other:
– Yes [specify]: traditional music

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:
– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
– Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Public education is mandated by the state in Vietnam. There is no other supplementary education in religious settings.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: A Romanized version of Raglai language has been used since the early 20th century. The language is not widely used in published sources, religious, or secular, however.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: as most individuals in the group will have learned Vietnamese. Literacy in Vietnamese became increasingly high in the middle of the 20th century through public secular school systems.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Although only a plurality of the members of the group have become recognized for published works in Vietnamese language

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: However, members of the group may have historically attended religious ceremonies in Cham Ahier communities in accordance with the Cham calendar.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, as there is a secular state calendar that is used in Vietnam.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism

- Cannibalism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Fishing
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards